

Editor and reviewer certificate

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This is to certificate that

Daniel Droguett

Has acted as an editor/reviewer for Mouth journal (ISSN 0719-7659) and is eligible for **10 hours of continuing professional development activities in 2016.**

Signed: César Rivera orcid.org/0000-0002-5491-4233.
Editor-in-Chief, Mouth

Oral Diseases Research Group maintains a database of reviewers' and editors' activities for the purpose of recording continuing professional development.